

Applying human factors science to strengthen bidirectional Global Health Partnerships

Chukwuemeka L. Anyikwa^{1*}, James Glasbey², Chukwuebuka E. Ogwo³, Peter A. Brennan⁴

Correspondence: Chukwuemeka L. Anyikwa, 1College of Medicine, University of Nigeria, Ituku-Ozalla Enugu, Nigeria. Email: Anyikwaemeka@gmail.com

1. College of Medicine, University of Nigeria, Ituku-Ozalla Enugu, Nigeria
2. NIHR Global Health Research Unit on Global Surgery, University of Birmingham, UK
3. Harvard School of Dental Medicine Boston, MA, USA
4. Queen Alexandra Hospital Portsmouth, UK

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Global health initiatives have historically focused on transferring resources and organizing short-term medical missions. While these efforts are often driven by good intentions, they frequently overlook the place of the human systems that underpin clinical care, team functioning and institutional resilience. In global surgery, for instance, the delivery of sophisticated equipment or surgical skills alone rarely leads to sustained improvements when critical elements such as providing technical training, workflow ergonomics, error reduction and communication patterns are neglected^{1,2}. This commentary proposes that integrating human factors science into the very foundation of global surgery partnerships is essential for building strong, adaptive human resources. In doing so, we move beyond one-way models of support and can shift the unidirectional support toward reciprocal collaboration, transforming global surgery and broader health exchanges into equitable ventures.

Surgery in low and middle income countries is under prioritised in terms of service needs, training, research and quality assurance, with patients in these settings facing a three times higher risk of postoperative mortality than patients in high income countries^{3,4}. To begin to address these challenges, the GlobalSurg research collaborative was established in 2013 as a network of 1500 hospitals across 140 countries, through which outcomes for more than 250,000 surgical patients have been recorded. In November 2016, an inaugural prioritisation meeting was held in Birmingham, bringing together 22 surgeons from 16 low and middle income countries to finalise a protocol for the first randomised trial targeting reduction of postoperative wound infections after abdominal surgery^{5,6}.

Building on this initiative, the NIHR Unit on Global Surgery established a platforms that empowered clinicians, patients and health systems in low and middle income countries to identify priority questions, co-design context specific interventions and generate evidence.¹ Human factors science has been integral to the success of such initiatives, adopting behaviour change theory to create more sustainable operating theatres, considering workforce planning at the heart of surgical preparedness, and building implementation science into intervention design and post-trial adoption and monitoring⁷.

To work effectively in complex health systems, partnerships should embrace four core principles from human factors science⁸. First, contextual alignment. This requires that all partners explore tasks and workflow using techniques such as observation (ethnography) and task mapping to ensure that innovations respect local priorities, constraints and cultural practices^{8,9}. Second, bidirectional learning. This acknowledges that both high income and low-income settings offer valuable insights and innovations in resource optimization and problem solving.^{8,10} Third, participatory design. This means involving frontline clinicians at every stage from needs assessment through to evaluation, fostering genuine shared ownership and trust^{8,11}. Fourth, continuous feedback. This requires simple data capture tools and debriefing sessions to support adaptation and accountability^{8,9}.

Policy and practice must evolve to prioritise human factors expertise as an essential component of global health partnerships. Funding agencies and academic institutions should support and incentivize skill building

in systems ergonomics, cross cultural communication and implementation science rooted in human factors principles. This could also be reflected in training programs and curricula in global surgery. There is an opportunity to broaden research priorities and outcomes measurement sets to include non-technical, implementation and process measures which will improve impact.

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References

1. Quene TM, Bust L, Louw J, Mwandri M, Chu KM. Global surgery is an essential component of global health. *Surgeon*. 2022;20(1):9–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surge.2021.10.001>
2. Shouhed D, Gewertz B, Wiegmann D, Catchpole K. Integrating human factors research and surgery: a review. *Arch Surg*. 2012;147(12):1141–6. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamasurg.2013.596>
3. National Institute for Health Research Global Health Research Unit on Global Surgery. Prioritizing research for patients requiring surgery in low- and middle-income countries. *Br J Surg*. 2019;106(2):e113–20. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.11037>
4. Mughal NA, Hussain MH, Ahmed KS, Waheed MT, Munir MM, Diehl TM, Zafar SN. Barriers to Surgical Outcomes Research in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Scoping Review. *J Surg Res*. 2023;290:188–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2023.04.017>
5. Monahan M, Glasbey J, Roberts TE, Jowett S, Pinkney T, Bhangu A, Morton DG, de la Medina AR, Ghosh D, Ademuyiwa AO, Ntirenganya F, Tabiri S, NIHR Global Research Health Unit on Global Surgery. The costs of surgical site infection after abdominal surgery in middle-income countries: Key resource use In Wound Infection (KIWI) study. *J Hosp Infect*. 2023;136:38–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhin.2023.03.023>
6. GlobalSurg Collaborative. Surgical site infection after gastrointestinal surgery in high-income, middle-income, and low-income countries: a prospective, international, multicentre cohort study. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2018;18(5):516–25. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(18\)30101-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(18)30101-4)
7. GlobalSurg Collaborative. Pooled analysis of WHO Surgical Safety Checklist use and mortality after emergency laparotomy. *Br J Surg*. 2019;106(2):e103–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bjs.11051>
8. Amisi JA, Cuba-Fuentes MS, Johnston EM, Makwero M, Prasad S, Ras T, Szkwarko D, von Pressentin K. A pragmatic approach to equitable global health partnerships in academic health sciences. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2023;8(5):e011522. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2022-011522>
9. Brennan PA, Mitchell DA, Holmes S, Plint S, Parry D. Good people who try their best can have problems: recognition of human factors and how to minimise error. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg*. 2016;54(1):3–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjoms.2015.09.023>
10. Sheikh K, Agyepong I, Jhalani M, Ammar W, Hafeez A, Pyakuryal S, Abimbola S, Ghaffar A, Swaminathan S. Learning health systems: an empowering agenda for low-income and middle-income countries. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10223):476–7. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)33134-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)33134-4)
11. Kruk ME, Gage AD, Arsenuault C, Jordan K, Leslie HH, Roder-DeWan S, et al. High-quality health systems in the Sustainable Development Goals era: time for a revolution. *Lancet Glob Health*. 2018;6(11):e1196–e1252. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30386-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30386-3)